

INFLUENCE OF VARIOUS DEFECTS ON THE QUALITY AND THE DURABILITY OF COMPOSITE PIPES

Philippe Castaing^{1*}, Alain Dessarthe¹, Alain Lemasçon¹, Didier LeYhuélic¹, Hubert Mallard²

¹ *Department of Polymers & Composites, CETIM, 74, route de la Jonelière, BP82617, 44326 Nantes Cedex 3, France*

¹ *Department of Mechanical Calculations, CETIM, 74, route de la Jonelière, BP82617, 44326 Nantes Cedex 3, France*

* : to whom all correspondence should be addressed (philippe.castaing@cetim.fr)

SUMMARY: The purpose of this document is to review tests concerning the quality and the durability of composite pipes in which various defects were inserted during the manufacturing process. The material studied are of three types : a glass fibre - orthophthalic polyester (ORTHO), a glass fibre - isophthalic polyester (ISO) and a glass fibre - DGEBA epoxy pipes (EPOXY). Regarding the defects inserted during manufacturing, the aim is to evaluate the :

- influence of the rate of fibre impregnation by resin,
- influence of the cure,
- influence of the rate of catalysts for the polyester pipes,
- influence of the winding angle,
- influence of the glass fiber humidity,

on the quality and durability. Various properties like thermal (rate of cure, glass transition temperatures), physical (void volumic ratio, fibre ratio, winding angles, weight, thickness) and mechanical ones are measured according to standards. Moreover, non destructive tests are performed. Ageing tests allow a comparison between the behaviour of the latter pipes.

KEYWORDS: quality, durability, glass fiber reinforced pipes, defects, manufacturing

1- INTRODUCTION

This paper review tests concerning the quality and the durability of composites pipes in which various defects were inserted during the manufacturing process. Pipes are widely used in the offshore oil industry, chemical industry or for heating systems, generally in an aggressive environment, and it appears to be of a great interest to know more about the influence of some manufacturing defects on the long term behaviour. The material studied are of three types : a glass fibre - orthophthalic polyester (ORTHO), a glass fibre - isophthalic polyester (ISO) and a glass fibre - DGEBA epoxy pipes (EPOXY).

The variations in the manufacturing, inducing defects inside the pipes, are as follows :

- rate of fibre impregnation by the resin,
- rate of catalysts for the polyester pipes, post-cure,
- winding angle,
- glass fiber humidity.

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the influence of the latter parameters on the quality and durability. Various properties like thermal (rate of cure, glass transition temperatures), physical (void volumic ratio, fibre ratio, winding angles) and mechanical ones are measured according to standards. Concerning the void volumic ratio, the fibre ratio and the winding angle, accurate data are obtained from the image analysis. These micromechanical data are used to optimize the mechanical calculation.

The mechanical properties of the plies are calculated using the Halpin-Tsai equations which combine parallel and serial springs. The laminate behaviour is then calculated using the laminate theory which can be improved at different orders.

The results are compared to the experimental mechanical characteristics such as the ultimate stress and strain according to a tensile test on rings (Nol tensile test) and the ultimate stress, strain and the modulus according to a flexural test. A statistical analysis of the results (Weibull) is used in order to focus on the failure probability.

The acoustic emission analysis allows us to rank the behaviour of the pipes according to the nature of the resin and to their initial defects.

The pipes are immersed in fresh water at high temperature for 1000 hours. Referring to previous studied performed on laminates¹, the aging is performed at the temperature of 60°C. Indeed, these accelerated tests lead to a correct degree of acceleration of the degradation, compared to a natural ageing in sea water. In addition, these temperatures prevent from leading to other thermal degradations due to glass transitions.

Finally, these tests allow a comparison between the three kinds of pipes.

2- MATERIALS STUDIED

The material studied are of three types : a glass fibre - orthophthalic polyester (ORTHO), a glass fibre - isophthalic polyester (ISO) and a glass fibre - DGEBA epoxy pipes (EPOXY), diameter : 120 mm. The molded pipes are one meter long. The reference pipes are manufactured by filament winding with a constant angle of winding equal to 55° for the ISO and EPOXY pipes, 30° and 55° for the ORTHO pipes. The reinforcement is a E glass fibre (800 tex) roving. In order to obtain a total thickness of 6 mm, 5 layers of helicoïdal windings at $-\alpha$ and 5 at $+\alpha$ were necessary. The curing was completed in an oven for 2 hours at 80°C in the case of the polyester pipes, for 3 hours at 140°C for the epoxy pipes.

The moulding is performed on a 5 axes filament winding and numerical Forplex machine.

3- VARIATIONS IN THE MANUFACTURING

The variations in the manufacturing conditions are displayed in the following table² :

Table 1: Pipes manufactured according various conditions

N° pipe	Manufacturing conditions	% Initiator	% Accelerator	Mf %	σ_r MPa	ϵ_r %	Tg °C	ΔH (j/g)
1	UP ortho, $\pm 30^\circ$, standard conditions	1	0,1	65	47	1,8	95,9	-4,0
2	UP ortho, $\pm 30^\circ$, no post cure	1	0,1	67	48	1,5	82,9	-4,4
3	UP ortho, $\pm 30^\circ$, promotor rate :-	1	0,05	67	53	1,6	74,1	-8,1

4	UP ortho, $\pm 30^\circ$, catalyst rate : -	0,5	0,1	66	55	1,3	86,7	-3,9
5	UP ortho, $\pm 55^\circ$, standard conditions	1	0,1	70	290	4,3	94,5	-4,6
6	Epoxyde, $\pm 55^\circ$, standard conditions	90 pp	1 pp	68	270	5,8	118,6	-2,0
7	UP ortho, $\pm 45^\circ$, standard conditions	1	0,1	69	115	5,0	92,6	-3,4
8	UP ortho, $\pm 30^\circ$, impregnation : -	1	0,1	71	38	0,9	93,6	-5,2
9	UP ortho, $\pm 30^\circ$, fibers in water	1	0,1	72	32	1,6	90,6	-5,0
10	UP ortho, $\pm 30^\circ$, dried fibers	1	0,1	70	53	1,3	95,7	-5,7
11	UP ortho, $\pm 87^\circ$, standard conditions	1	0,1	71	870	5,4	79,8	-5,2
12	UP Iso, $\pm 55^\circ$, standard conditions	1	0,1	68	246	4,7	117,4	-4,6

Standard conditions : as described in § 2. During the post cure, in an oven, the pipes are in rotation to prevent resin flowing due to gravity.

No post cure : the pipes are cured at room temperature.

Accelerator (cobalt octoate) rate - = rate 0,05 % instead of 0,1 %.

Initiator (MEKP) rate - = rate 0,5% instead of 1%.

Impregnation : - = the impregnation of the fibres with resin is weak (low resin ratio).

Fibers in water : before impregnation, the fibres are immersed in water.

Dried fibers : a layer (the 3rd) consisting in unwetted fibres is wound.

4- QUALITY CONTROL

4-1- Thermal and physical controls³

They are performed on the various pipes by differential scanning calorimetry, in order to determine Tg and the residual crosslinking enthalpy ΔH (J/g).

The max Tg obtained in the best manufacturing conditions should be :

Orthophthalic resin (S2010V from Cray Valley) : Tg = 96°C

Isophthalic resin (G703 from Cray Valley) : Tg = 117°C

Epoxy Dgeba LY 556 + hardener HY917 (from Ciba) : Tg = 120°C

Analysis conditions : from 50° to 220°C, $u=10^\circ\text{C}/\text{mn}$, $P_{\text{nitrogen}} = 1.5$ b, standard ISO 11357-1

The influence of the post-cure at room temperature compared to post cure in oven appears clearly (-13°C in Tg), as well as the influence of a low rate of initiator and accelerator (-20° to -10°C in Tg). The impregnation of wet fibres may inhibit the cross linking reaction (-5° to -6° in Tg). Pipes n° 7 and 11 were probably bad post cured. The conditions of standard cure lead to values of Tg close to maxima l ones.

The weight resin ratios are determined by calcination (standard NFT 57-102), volumic ratios, porosity rates and winding angles by image analysis. As an evidence, the weight fibre ratio is higher for pipes with bad impregnation of resin (dried fibres in Table 1).

4-2- Mechanical testing⁴

The mechanical characteristics such as the ultimate stress and strain are determined according to a tensile test on rings (10 mm wide), the rigidity according to a flexural test on wide rings (100 mm wide). Tensile test on rings according to ASTM D 2290-76 standard.

Compressive –flexural- test on wide rings according to ASTM D 2412-77 standard.

The influence of manufacturing parameters and of the angle, as well as the nature of the resin, are displayed on Figures 1 and 2.

Fig. 1: Influence of manufacturing parameters on the failure stress (MPa) – ortho pipes $\pm 30^\circ$

Fig. 2: Influence of winding angle and of the resin on the failure stress (MPa)

- Influence of manufacturing : among the UP ($\pm 30^\circ$) ortho pipes, the rupture stress is the highest for pipes n° 3 and 4, the lowest for pipe n°10.
- Influence of winding angle : the test on pipe n°11 ($\pm 87^\circ$) corresponds to a tensile test in the direction of the fibres., and so leads to a higher stress. The main stress applied on the other rings ($\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$) is a shear one, and the lowest values of rupture stresses are obtained for samples with a $\pm 30^\circ$ winding angle.
- Influence of the chemical nature of the resin : the difference observed are not significant.

The probability P of the fibre fracture under a stress σ is given by the following distribution :

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right] \quad (1)$$

where m and σ_0 are factors of the Weibull distribution. m=8, $\sigma_0 = 306$ MPa for the Ortho $\pm 30^\circ$ pipe, m=22, $\sigma_0 = 860$ MPa for the Ortho $\pm 55^\circ$ pipe.

Fig. 3: Probability of failure for two kinds of pipes (Ortho $\pm 30^\circ$, mean rupture stress : 288 MPa; Ortho $\pm 55^\circ$, mean rupture stress : 870 MPa)

The flexural test on a wide ring (100 mm wide) leads to an evaluation of the radial modulus¹ on the $\pm 45^\circ$ pipe, $E_r = 11300$ MPa. A comparison of the mechanical characteristics determined both by calculation and by mechanical testing is displayed in the following table.

Table 2: Comparison between the mechanical characteristics calculated and measured

angle	Flexural tests				Tensile tests		
	Flexural modulus (MPa) by calculation	Flexural modulus (MPa) by calculation	Rupture σ (MPa)	Mode of rupture	Rupture σ (MPa) calculated	Rupture σ (MPa) measured	Mode of rupture
$\pm 55^\circ$	17047		126	Shear	201	287	Shear
$\pm 87^\circ$	38208		896	Fibres	968	870	Fibres
$\pm 45^\circ$	11500	11300	69	Tranverse S	87	115	
$\pm 30^\circ$	10789		41	Tranverse S	40	47	Tranverse S

The moduli calculated and measured for the pipe $\pm 45^\circ$ are close to each other. The rupture stresses obtained by mechanical testing are generally higher than those calculated.

4-3- Acoustic emission

The acoustic emission (AE) analysis allows us to rank the behaviour of the pipes according to the nature of the resin and to their initial defects. The static failure process can be analyzed from the acoustic emission recorded during loading. From experimental results, during the quasi static loading applied to a sample (tensile test), there is a relationship between the stress level and a given acoustic activity. That latter stress is then correlated to the failure stress (or to the modulus...). The acoustic activity will start with a various delay due to the manufacturing conditions or due to the state of the material². Different activity criteria are considered :

- a cumulative activity of 2000 to 5000 counts,
- a rate of activity of 500 to 2000 counts.

The failure of pipes n°8, 9 and 10 (pipes with bad resin impregnation or wet fibres) lead to an AE activity five times lower than the one of the other pipes. The lower the AE signal amplitude, the longer the AE signal duration.

- influence of manufacturing parameters (Ortho $\pm 30^\circ$ pipes) see Figures 4 and 5.

The first criteria leads to a better correlation with the failure stress, but the dispersion remains high. Pipe n°1 (standard conditions) does not get the best behaviour, pipes n° 10 and 8 highlight with their low mechanical properties as well as early acoustic activity.

Fig. 4 : Influence of manufacturing parameters – acoustic emission correlated to rupture stress

- influence of the matrix

The test are performed on $\pm 55^\circ$ ortho, iso and epoxy samples. The best behaviour is observed for the glass reinforced epoxy pipe, for which the activity is later than for the other pipes.

Fig. 5 : Influence of manufacturing parameters – acoustic emission correlated to modulus

- influence of the winding angle (Figure 6)

Whatever is the winding angle, a relationship between the stress rupture and the acoustic emission initiation stress, linked to the first significant damage, is found :

$$\sigma_{\text{first activity}} = 0.55 \sigma_{\text{rupture}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 6 : Influence of winding angle on first activity stress correlated to rupture stress

5- DURABILITY

The 0,8 m long pipes (GFR ortho, iso, epoxy at $\pm 55^\circ$) are then immersed in distilled water at a temperature of 60°C and ambient pressure for 1000 hours. Referring to previous studies performed on laminates^{1,2,5,6}, the tests at $T=60^\circ\text{C}$ as lead to a correct degree of acceleration of the degradation, compared to a natural ageing in water (acceleration factor of about 25 to 30, that is to say that 1000 hours at 60° may be equivalent to about 5 to 10 years in fresh water at 20°C); in addition, this temperature prevents from leading to other thermal degradations^{1,2,5,6}.

The period of 1000 hours of testing corresponds to the plasticization of the matrix, without hydrolytic attack, as shown in a previous study. The absorption of water in pipes can be predicted by Fick's model, in polar coordinates for pipes with an internal radius a and an external radius b . At steady state, for a pipe in total immersion, the general solution is :

$$C(r) = c_1 \cdot [\ln(b/r) + \ln(r/a)] / (\ln(b/a)) \quad (3)$$

where c_1 is the water concentration on both side of the thickness pipe. The water concentration profile $C(r)$ through the thickness of the cylinder is no more linear as for a plane sheet, as the quantity of molecules crossing a surface A at r would cross a surface $A+dA$ at $r+dr$; A is constant for the plane case. A specific decrease of absorption for $0,6 < M(t)/M_s < 0,9$ is then observed compared to plane sheets.

However, when $(b-a)/a \ll 1$ et $b/a \geq 1$, $b/a \approx 1$, the pipe tends to behave like a plane sheet, which is useful to determine the diffusivity D , and to predict the sorption curves of hollow cylinders the same way as for plane sheets.

The experimental procedure itself consists in monitoring the weight of water absorbed, and in measuring the characteristics (thermal and mechanical ones) at the end of the ageing test. The mean absorption of three pipes is determined. Figure 7 reports some experimental weight measurements.

Figure 7 : Classical absorption curves of ISO pipes (dried fibres or not) and ORTHO pipes (dried fibres = impregnation -; standard conditions), in distilled water at 60°C .

The ISO and EPOXY pipes tends to reach the saturation state, on the other hand it appears that the ORTHO resin begins being hydrolyzed (decrease of the curve $M(t) \%$ as hydrolyzed products are rejected from the materials. Curiously, D and $M_s (\%)$ for materials with low resin rate ("dried fibres") are higher than for the correct materials : a preferential absorption and diffusion along the interfaces fibres-matrix certainly occurs.

Table 3 : Diffusional parameters of the materials studied

MATERIAL	D (mm ² /h x 10 ³)	Ms (%)	D (mm ² /h x 10 ³) low resin %	Ms (%) low resin %
ORTHO	8.6	1.25	13.5	1.52
ISO	7.2	1.05	7.8	1.11
EPOXY	7.5	1.10	7.9	1.20

The diffusivity of water and the saturation rate of the ORTHO resin is higher than for the other materials, this difference is explained by the chemical hydrophilic behaviour of the orthophthalic acid and by the unsaturation rate lower than for the other polyester resin.

The mechanical characteristics measured are the ultimate stress and strain according a tensile test on rings (NoI tensile test, standard ASTM D 2290-76). The results are presented in the following tables (Table 4). The results of flexural tests (wide rings) are presented in Table 5. Tests are performed on "humid" samples, just after ageing, and on "dried" samples, after being dried in room conditions for one month.

Table 4 : Tensile tests performed on rings at initial state, after ageing (humid state) and after ageing on dried samples

Pipe	Initial state		1000 h Humid state		1000 h Dry state	
	Xr	Ar%	Xr	Ar%	Xr	Ar%
ORTHO	238,4	4,10	138,0	3,65	172,0	3,44
ISO	250,1	3,87	195,6	3,68	213,3	3,35
EPOXY	270,43	5,33	217,59	5,39	238,9	4,14

Table 5 : Flexural tests on large rings at initial state and after 1000 hours of ageing, (dried samples)

Material	σ 1 st failure (MPa)	E circonf. (MPa)	σ rupt (MPa)
ORTHO EI	392,00	11469,05	425,17
ORTHO EV	246,34	15499,56	286,21
ISO EI			383,36
ISO EV	295,24	12471,45	327,21
EPOXY EI			520,77
EPOXY EV	321,06	12124,79	336,40

Generally after an ageing, Ar% increases which is, surprisingly, not the case for these pipes : a loss of 10% of Ar% is observed on ORTHO humid samples, 5% for humid ISO samples, +1% for EPOXY but this latter results is not significant. Regarding the ultimate stresses Xr, the loss is -42% for the ORTHO, -22% for the ISO and -19% for the EPOXY pipes.

Looking at the results obtained for "dried samples", it appears that the ultimate stresses increase compared to the humid state after ageing.

So the % of loss due to the plasticization with water and to the differential swelling inducing microcracks, is as follows :

- 15% of loss for Xr (ORTHO pipe)
- 8% of loss for Xr (ISO pipe)
- 7,5% of loss for Xr (EPOXY pipe)

The results of thermal analyses are exposed in Table 6.

Table 6 : Values of Tg (°C) after ageing, for various pipes

Material	Initial State Tg(°C)	After ageing Tg(°C) "humid state"	After ageing Tg (°C) "dry state"
ORTHO	95,9	90,2	90,9
ISO	118,9	113,1	116,0
EPOXY	119,0	105,2	115,6

The results show that the ORTHO resin begins being hydrolyzed very early compared to the other materials, which recover partly their thermal properties. The Epoxy resin is more sensitive to plasticization regarding the thermal properties.

6- CONCLUSION

This study focuses on the major effect of some parameters on the quality and durability of pipes⁷. It remains important to consider that the various characteristics of a pipe may be affected during its life-time in contact with water, and it appears to be essential to control completely their manufacture to prevent from in-service early aging or failures.

REFERENCES

1. Ph. Castaing, H. Mallard, "Effect of Plasticization with Water on the Behaviour of Long Term Exposed Filament Composites", Progress in Durability Analysis of Composite Systems, Cardon, Fukuda & Reifsnider eds., Balkema Ed, 1996, pp 233-239.
2. Ph. Castaing, A. Dessarthe, A. Lemasçon, D. LeYhuélic, H. Mallard, Internal Report n°185301 "Quality Control of Composite Pipes", *in french*, CETIM, Dept. Polymers & Composites, (1993).
3. Ph. Castaing, H. Mallard, "Quantitative Image Analysis for the Microstructural Study and the Calculation of Filament Structures", Proc. of ECCM CTS 2, 1994, pp 437-445
4. D. Le Yhuélic, Ph. Castaing, H. Mallard, Durabilité des Matériaux Composites : de l'essai de laboratoire à l'essai d'homologation industrielle : cas de tubes en composite, Mécanique Industrielle et Matériaux, vol. 50, n°3, 1997, pp 112-115.
5. Ph. Castaing, L. Lemoine, "Effects of Water Absorption and Osmotic Degradation on Long-Term Behavior of Glass Fiber Reinforced Polyester", J. Polymer Composites, Vol. 16, n°5, 1995, pp 349-356.
6. Ph. Castaing, A. Lemasçon, "Improvement of the Quality and of the Durability of Composite Parts owing to Failure Analysis", *in french*, Journée Durabilité AMAC, 12/05/1998.
7. H. Mallard, S. Durand, Ph. Castaing, Composite Pipe Mechanics, CD Rom to be published, CETIM Ed, 1999.